

A Review on Plant Leaf Disease Detection using KNN Algorithm

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ABSTRACT

Software has always been a companion for humans since the boomed invention of automation. All the automation which has been done till date always carried a motive for the ease of complex processes and sometimes for replacing enormous human activities. The project presents plant leaf disease detection, effect of disease on plant yield and the remedies for its cure. In agriculture, research of automatic plant disease is essential in monitoring large fields of plants, and thus automatically detect symptoms of disease as soon as they appear on plant leaves. Every other field has got some benefit from new technologies as compared to the agricultural field. According to past studies, 42% of agricultural production is in loss and that too because of the increasing rate of loss due to plant leaf diseases. To overcome this major issue, this plant leaf disease detection technique can be applied to detect a disease from the input images. This process involved steps like image preprocessing, image segmentation, feature extraction.

Keywords: Plant Leaf Detection, Image processing, k-mean clustering algorithm, GLCM, Classification, SVM, KNN

INTRODUCTION

India is a country with a majority of the population relying heavily on the agricultural sector. The crop cultivation area in India spans around 3,50,000 hectares approximately and the production quantities roughly sum up to 53,00,000 tons, making India the third largest agricultural producer in the world. The sensitivity of crops coupled with climatic conditions have made blights common in the crop during all the stages of its growth. Blight affected leaves constitute 10-30% of the total crop loss. Identification of such blights in the leaf is very important in preventing any heavy losses in yield as well as the quantity of the agricultural product. Monitoring the leaf blights manually is a difficult task due to its complex nature and is a time consuming process. Therefore, there is a need to reduce the manual effort put into this task, while making accurate predictions and ensuring that the farmer's lives are hassle free. Visually observable patterns are difficult to decipher at a single glance, leading to many farmers making inaccurate assumptions regarding the blight. As a result, prevention mechanisms taken by the farmers may be ineffective and sometimes harmful. Farmers usually come together and implement common blight prevention mechanisms, as they lack expert advice on how to deal with their crop infestation. There have been circumstances where due to inadequate knowledge or misinterpretation regarding the intensity of the blight, over-dosage or under-dosage of the pesticide has resulted in crop damage. This is the underlying motivation for the proposed methodology that aims to accurately detect and classify blights in the crop.

The methodology suggested in the paper pertains to the most common blights found in the leaf like, Bacterial leaf spot and Septoria leaf spot, Yellow Leaf Curl among many others. Any leaf image given as input can be classified into one of the blight classes or can be deemed healthy. The dataset used for evaluation is a subset of Leaf Village, a repository that contains 54,306 images of 14 crops infested with 26 blights. The subset includes around 18160 images of different leaf blights. Broadly, the proposed methodology consists of three major steps: data acquisition, pre-processing and classification. The images used for the implementation of the proposed methodology were acquired from a publicly available dataset called Leaf Village, as mentioned earlier. In the next step, the images were resized to a standard size before feeding it into the classification model. Agriculture is vital to one's survival. A crucial to why husbandry is

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important to business and society is its affair — from producing raw accoutrements to contributing to the global force chain and profitable development. Agriculture provides utmost of the world's food and fabrics, In discrepancy to the agrarian sector, every other assiduity has served from new technologies in some way. But, Because of technological improvements similar as detectors, widgets, outfit, and information technology, ultramodern granges and agrarian operations operate veritably else from those just a many decades ago. substantially, there are numerous ways developed in detecting and prognosticating factory conditions. one of them is through image processing and machine literacy. Image processing is a system of performing operations on an image in order to ameliorate it or prize useful information from it. It's a type of signal processing in which the input is an image and the affair can be an image or image characteristics features. Image processing is significant in a number of Deep Learning- grounded Computer Vision operations, where similar preprocessing can significantly ameliorate model performance. In this paper we're using MATLAB software and some algorithms to reuse an image.

Machine literacy(ML) is a type of artificial intelligence(AI) that allows software operations to come more accurate at prognosticating issues without being explicitly programmed to do so. Machine Learning algorithms use literal data as input to prognosticate new affair values. Machine literacy is the field of study that gives computers the capability to learn without explicitly programmed. ML is one of the most investigative technologies that one would have come across. As it's apparent from the name, it gives the computer that makes it more analogous to mortal The capability to learn. Here we're using machine literacy because it's substantially used for vaccination and bracket and as it's recommended to prognosticate the factory conditions at the early stage of in the field of husbandry is essential to feed the food to the overall population but it's unfortunate to prognosticate the complaint at the early stage of the crops. The main end of this paper involves enhancement of delicacy in detecting conditions by being machine literacy ways. The input we're taking is an image and the affair which we get is the detected complaint and it's classified group.

LITERATURE SURVEY

Classification of Pomegranate Diseases Based On Back Backpropagation Neural Network [1]

S Sannakki and V.S. Rajpurohit, proposed a “Classification of Pomegranate Diseases Based on Back Propagation Neural Network”[1] which mainly works on the method of segment(The affected area , color and texture) are used as the features. Here they have used neural network classifier for the classification .Backpropagation is the essence of neural network training. It is the method of fine-tuning the weights of a neural network based on the error rate obtained in the previous epoch (i.e., iteration). Proper tuning of the weights allows you to reduce error rates and make the model reliably increasing its generalization. Backpropagation in neural network is a short form for “backward propagation of errors.”It is a standard method of training artificial neural networks. This method helps calculate the gradient of a loss function with respect to all the weights in the network. The main advantage is it converts to L^*a^*b to extract chromaticity layers of the image and categorization is found to be 97.30% . The main disadvantage is that it is used only for the limited crops.

Cotton Leaf Disease Identification Using Pattern Recognition Techniques [2]

R Rothe and R.V .Kshirsagar introduced a “Cotton leaf disease identification using pattern recognition techniques”[2] which uses snake segmentation , here Hu’s moments are used as distinctive attribute. Active contour model used to limit the vitality inside the infection spot, BPNN classifier tackles the numerous class problems. The average classification is found to be 85.52%. Pattern recognition is achieved by utilizing the concept of learning. Learning enables the pattern recognition system to be trained and to become adaptable to provide more accurate results. A section of the dataset is used for training the system while the rest is used for testing it. Pattern recognition is the use of machine learning algorithms to identify

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patterns. It classifies data based on statistical information or knowledge gained from patterns and their representation. In this technique, labeled training data is used to train pattern recognition systems. A label is attached to a specific input value that is used to produce a pattern-based output.

Leaf Disease Detection and Grading Using Computer Vision Technology and Fuzzy Logic [3]

Aakanksha Rastogi, Ritika Arora and Shanu Sharma proposed a “Leaf disease detection and grading using computer vision technology and fuzzy logic”[3]. This paper imparts a simple and computationally proficient method used for leaf disease identification and grading using digital image processing and machine vision technology. The proposed system is divided into two phases, in the first phase the plant is recognized on the basis of the features of leaf, it includes pre-processing of leaf images, and feature extraction followed by Artificial Neural Network based training and classification for recognition of leaf. In the second phase the disease present in the leaf is classified, this process includes K-Means based segmentation of defected area, feature extraction of defected portion and the ANN based classification of disease. Then the disease grading is done on the basis of the amount of disease present in the leaf. Here K-means clustering is used to segment the defected area ; GLCM algorithm is for the extraction of texture features ,Fuzzy logic is used for the disease grading. They used an artificial neural network(ANN) as a classifier which mainly helps to check the severity of the diseased leaf.

Automated Vision-Based Diagnosis of Banana Bacterial Wilt Disease And Black Sigatoka Disease [4]

Godliver Owomugisha, John A. Quinn, Ernest Mwebaze and James L was proposed “Automated vision-based diagnosis of banana bacterial wilt disease and black sigatoka disease”[4]. In this paper they have described that there are machine learning techniques which have been used in an attempt to detect diseases in the banana plant such as banana bacterial wilt (BBW) and banana black sigatoka (BBS) that have caused a huge loss to many banana growers. Hence, here the study investigated various computer vision techniques which led to the development of an algorithm that consists of four main phases. In phase one, images of banana leaves were acquired using a standard digital camera. Phase two involves use of different feature extraction techniques to obtain relevant data to be used in phase three where images are classified as either healthy or diseased. Of the seven classifiers that were used in this study, Extremely Randomized Trees performed best in identifying the diseases achieving 0.96 AUC for BBW and 0.91 for BBS. Colour histograms are extracted and transformed from RGB TO HSV, HSV to L*a*b. Peak components are used and area under the curve analysis is used for classification. They used nearest neighbors, Decision tree, random forest, extremely randomized tree, Naive Bayes and SV Classifier.

SVM-Based Multiple Classifier System for Recognition Of Wheat Leaf Diseases [5]

Uan Tian ,Chunjiang Zhao, Shenglian Lu and Xinyu Guo proposed a ”SVM-Based Multiple Classifier System for Recognition of Wheat Leaf Diseases”[5], This paper presents a SVM-based Multiple Classifier System (MCS) for pattern recognition of wheat leaf diseases. The proposed system uses stacked generalization structures to combine the classification decisions obtained from three kinds of support vector machines (SVMs)-based classifiers. And three different feature sets including color features, texture features and shape features are used as training sets for three corresponding classifiers. Firstly, these different feature sets are classified by the classifiers in low-level of MCS to different corresponding mid-level categories, which are partly described by the symptom of crop diseases according to the knowledge of plant pathology. Then the mid-level features are extracted from these mid-categories produced from low-level classifiers. Finally high-level SVMs will be trained and correct errors made by the color, texture and shape SVMs to

improve the performance of recognition.

The Detection and Classification of Leaf Diseases Using Multiclass Support Vector Machines [6]

Yangon Myanmar, Ko Ko Zaw, Zin Ma Myo, and Wah Hlaing proposed “The detection and classification of leaf diseases using Multiclass Support Vector Machines [6]”, on 11th National Conference on Science and Engineering. In this paper, they have described a method of detection and classification of plant disease using image processing and machine learning techniques. They have used standard images of leaves of several types of plants to test our method. Initially, the method segments the input image to isolate disease parts of the leaf. Then the obtained result has various features from the diseased affected segmented image. Finally, the leaves are classified into healthy and disease types based on its features using the Multi-class Support Vector Machine (SVM) classifier. Experimental results indicate that this method yields a very high accuracy rate for detection and classification of plant diseases. SVM, is initially proposed for binary classification technique, with simple manipulation can be used for a multiple class case. This project also tries to attempt for improvement in classifying the leaf diseases. Most of the work involves extracting statistical features of RGB signals converted into LAB form.

A Survey of Disease Identification And Classification Through Leaf Images: A Computational Method [7]

Sukhvir Kaur, Shreelekha Pandey, Shivani Goel proposed “A Survey of Disease Identification and Classification Through Leaf Images: A Computational Method[7]”. Here the researchers have thus attempted to automate the process of plantdisease detection and classification utilized on computer vision technologies aspects. A discussion on commonly identify those that seem to work well across several crops or crop categories.

Design Innovations for 3c’s Compute Communicate Control Plant Disease Detection Using Machine Learning[8]

In 2018 in International Conference on “Design Innovations for 3C’s Compute Communicate Control Plant Disease Detection Using Machine Learning[8]” by Shima Ramesh, Mr. Ramachandra Hebbar, Niveditha M, Pooja R, Prasad Bhat N, Shashank N,Mr. P V Vinod proposed that according to past studies, 42% of agricultural production is in Loss, and thattoo solely as a result of plant leaf diseases. With this technique, plant leaf diseases can be detected from input images to overcome this major issue. This process involved steps like image pre-processing, image segmentation, feature extraction. On the basis of these three steps, K Nearest Neighbor (KNN) classification is applied. As a result of the proposed implementation, it has a 98.56% accuracy rate in predicting plant leaf diseases. This paper makes use of Random Forest algorithm in identifying between healthy and diseased leaf from the data sets created. Our proposed paper includes various phases of implementation namely dataset creation, feature extraction, training the classifier and classification.

The Detection of Plant Diseases and Pests using Deep Learning[9]

In 2021 in BMC(Biomed-central) Jun Liu and Xuewei Wang proposed “The detection of plant diseases and pests using deep learning[9]”.In this study, the evaluation of the performance results using different approaches of nine powerful architectures of deep neural networks for plant disease detection is done. Transfer learning and deep feature extraction methods are used, which adapt these deep learning models to the problem at hand. The utilized pre-trained deep models are considered in the presented work for feature extraction and for further fine-tuning. The obtained features using deep feature extraction are then classified by support vector machine (SVM), extreme learning machine (ELM), and K-nearest neighbor (KNN) methods. The experiments are carried out using data consisting of real disease and pest images from Turkey. The accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, and F1-score are all calculated for performance evaluation. The evaluation

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results show that deep feature extraction and SVM/ELM classification produced better results than transfer learning. In addition, the fc6 layers of the AlexNet, VGG16, and VGG19 models produced better accuracy scores when compared to the other layers. Here SVM is used for recognizing image samples. The accuracy of implementation is about 92% with a sufficient and stable dataset used for the project

Citrus Canker Detection Based On Leaf Images Analysis[10]

Min Zhang, and Qinggang Meng have proposed research on “Citrus canker detection based on leaf images analysis”. Citrus canker is a bacterial disease that causes lesions on the leaves, stems, and fruit of plants including citrus and other plants in the citrus family. Canker causes the citrus tree to continually decline in health and fruit production until the tree produces no fruit at all. Citrus canker is highly contagious and can be spread rapidly. Citrus canker is a quarantine disease which may cause huge damage to citrus production. Effective and fast disease detection methods must be undertaken to minimize the losses of citrus canker infection. In this paper, a new approach is presented to detect citrus canker from leaf images collected in the field. Firstly, a global canker lesion descriptor is used to detect citrus diseased-lesion from leaf-background. Then a zone-based combined local descriptor is proposed to identify citrus canker disease from other similar diseases-lesions. Thirdly, a two-level hierarchical detection structure is developed to identify the canker lesion and AdaBoost is adopted in feature selection and classifier learning.

PAPER	AUTHOR	METHOD	RESULT
[1]	S. Ramesh	KNN classifier	This paper has tested on 5 rare diseases, Early blight, Mosaic virus, Down mildew, White fly, Leaf miner etc. The main aim of this paper is that classifying and detecting of diseases using KNN classifier is more accurate because in this work that classifier has detected 5 diseases with 98.56% accuracy compared to SVM classifier which detected 2 diseases with less accuracy and also has some errors with it.
[2]	U. Shruthi, V. Nagaveni	Random forest classifier	In this paper, the author used Random forest classifier, the model was trained using 160 images of papaya leaves with less datasets with accuracy of 70% when compared to other machine learning approaches such as SVM, Gaussian, and Naive Bayes. The primary goal of this study is to use a Random forest classifier to determine if a leaf is infected or healthy.
[3]	J. Shirahatti, R. Patil and P. Akulwa	CNN classifier	This paper explained how Farmers gathered information earlier and data through the use of information technology and precision agriculture to make the best decisions for a high yield from the farm. Ultimately, according to this review, CNN classifier detects more diseases than other classifiers with an average accuracy of 96.3%.
[4]	P. Panchal, V. C. Raman and S. Mantr	SVM classifier	In this paper, The algorithms were tested on three diseases: Early Blight, Late Blight, and Bacterial Spot. This paper discusses many ways for automated computerised disease detection in plants, which can be accomplished using picture segmentation and classification methods. As a consequence of analysing the results, the random forest approach delivers reliable identification of plant leaf diseases while requiring minimal computer complexity

[5]	Daniya, T., and S. Vigneshwari	NN classifier	The main point made here is that classification utilising machine learning methods such as NN-based classifiers in detecting plant diseases has a higher accuracy of 95.5%. The primary goal of this work is to survey and summarise the detection of rice plant diseases using image processing and machine learning approaches. Various segmentation algorithms were used to retrieve the diseased leaf picture of a rice plant. The strategies discussed in this study assist researchers in overcoming the many difficulties that directly or indirectly influence society.
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PROBLEM STATEMENT

India is an agricultural country, where most of the population depends on agricultural products. So the cultivation can be improved by technological support. Diseases may be caused by pathogens in plants at any environmental condition. In most of the cases diseases are seen on the leaves of the plants, so the detection of disease plays an important role in successful cultivation of crops. There are lots of techniques to detect the different types of diseases in plants in its early stages. Conventional methods of plant disease detection in naked eye observation methods and it is non-effective for large crops. Using digital image processing and machine learning, disease detection in plants is efficient, less time consuming and accurate. This technique saves time, efforts, laborers and use of pesticides. Hope this approach will become a little contribution for agriculture fields.

OBJECTIVE

- To enhance the given input image by Image acquisition and Image pre-processing.
- Identify the affected part through texture analysis and Segmentation.
- Classify the healthy and affected leaf part by feature extraction and classification.
- Train the model by using testing data for accurate results.

Software has always been a companion for humans since the invention of automation. All the automation which has been done till date always carried a motive for the ease of complex process and sometimes for replacing enormous human activities. This project will be very helpful to farmers in rural areas and also will help them in saving their yields from diseases as farmers lose a huge amount of their cultivated crops because of diseases and this system will help them to avoid the similar situation. This project can also provide them cure by suggesting preventive measures and cure according to the prevailing disease and this project will also display and give an idea about the effect of crop disease on crop yield. The main goal of this project is to identify the most common diseases seen in Plant Leaf and suggest suitable measures to prevent them.

METHODOLOGIES

In this paper, the proposed methodology follows 4 basic steps. They are:

- **Pre-Processing Phase:**

The model uses matlab picture preparing library plant leaf image is as an input which is further converted to gray scale using GLCM technique.

- **Image Segmentation:**

The Image segmentation technique is applied which will segment the image on the basis of their properties. In this work, the region based k-mean segmentation technique is applied.

- **Feature Extraction:**

In this stage we have to extract the valuable sections. Diverse features are picked to depict the distinctive properties of the leaves using GLCM algorithm

- **Classification:**

In the classification stage, the co-event highlights for the leaves are extracted and contrasted and then compared it similarly to put away in the feature library. The main classifiers used here are SVM and KNN classifiers. Out of 2 algorithms KNN has shown 98.56% accuracy by detecting most affected area among all 4 detected diseases

Figure 1: flow chart of classification some algorithms

- **k- mean segmentation or k- mean clustering algorithm**

K Means is a clustering algorithm. Clustering algorithms are unsupervised algorithms means that there's no labeled data available. It's used to identify different classes or clusters in the given data grounded on how analogous the data is then, in this work, K- means clustering divides the splint image into four corridor/ cluster from which one or further corridor may contain the complaint which indicates that the splint is infected by multiple conditions.

- **KNN classifier**

KNN is a Supervised machine literacy fashion. K- NN algorithm assumes the similarity between the new case/ data and available cases and put the new case into the order that's utmost analogous to the available orders. Then, datasets are subordinated to 2 phases a) Training dataset b) Testing dataset Then, in this work, After Doing testing through KNN Classifier it shows exact complaint name for any number of splint diseases. The average delicacy produced by this fashion is 98.56.

Figure 2: KNN classifier

- **Image Acquisition**

First stage of factory complaint discovery system is image acquisition. High quality factory images can be acquired using digital cameras, scanners or drones

- **Annotated Dataset**

Knowledge Grounded datasets to be created for captured images with differen classes.

- **Image Processing**

Ameliorate some image features important for farther processing. Segmentation process is used to partition the factory image in colorful parts. This can be used for the birth of diseased area in splint, stem or root of factory from background.

- **Feature Extraction**

Birth of Colour, shape and texture point of complaint part of the factory can be done.using slate position Co-occurrence Matrix(GLCM), Blend vision and machine intelligence etc

- **Classification**

Eventually, any of the machine literacy ways can be used to classify the colorful conditions in shops.

Figure 3: flow chart of classification

- **Support Vector Machine (SVM):**

Support vector machine algorithm finds a hyperplane that distinctly classifies the data points. The hyperplane is an N-dimensional space (the number of features -N) which helps to classify the values. There are various methods to find a hyperplane in order to separate two data points but we need to find an optimal hyperplane which has a maximum margin (there

should be a maximum distance between two points of both the classes). it produces 88% accuracy by detecting diseases like bacterial spot, Early blight, Late blight.

Figure 4: SVM classifier

CONCLUSION

To prevent losses, small holder farmers are dependent on a timely and accurate crop disease diagnosis. This service is free, easy to use and requires just a smartphone and internet connection. Overall, this study is conclusive in demonstrating how KNN may be applied to empower small-holder farmers in their fight against plant disease. The final result was a plant disease detection app. In the future, work should be focused on diversifying training datasets and also in testing similar web applications in real life situations. Without such developments, the struggle against plant disease will continue. So Implementation of the project work was done successfully and we got to learn many more things from this project. Several options are now made possible by technology advancements in plant diagnostics However, when compared to other fields of production, there are still hurdles in making novel approaches available on a broad scale. It is worth emphasising in this regard that not only can preexisting and smart technologies like machine learning approach aid scientists in the fight against pandemic diseases, by detecting the diseases in proper time. Finally, the primary goal of this paper was to propose improvements to current classification algorithms for plant leaf disease detection using machine learning, which is supported by the KNN classifier, which outperforms the SVM classifier. In future, plant diseases may be predicted than detection which helps in retrieving the life of plant back without delay. There may be many approaches to solve this, like deep learning with various algorithms.

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